

DIGITAL GALLERY: Finlaggan - 1450

Lost medieval home of the Lords of the Isles

From left clockwise: Crucifix Part – 3D Model; Lords of the Isles App; drone footage of Finlaggan today; medieval Finlaggan reconstruction (Credit: Open Virtual Worlds).

In the late medieval period, Loch Finlaggan in Islay of the Inner Hebrides was an important power base. The two islands of Eilean Mor (or Large Isle) and Eilean na Comhairle (or Council Isle) on the loch were the site of a major residence of the Lords of the Isles, who governed the Hebrides and parts of mainland Scotland and Ulster. A complex of buildings spanned the two islands, connected by a causeway, and served as the administrative and ceremonial centre. Research has revealed the comfort and wealth of the area, with dogs wearing decorative collars, and the Lords and their followers enjoying music, imported wine and board games. The lordship was traditionally held by the MacDonald family, whose rule stretched from Antrim in Ireland to the north east of Scotland. During the late medieval period, the Scottish kings were trying to reign in the influence of the MacDonalds. In the 1490s, for instance, James IV sent a military expedition to sack Finlaggan, destroying many of the buildings. The site subsequently sank into obscurity.

Reconstructions

Medieval Finlaggan – 1450 Reconstruction [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4748691](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748691)

Drawing on the findings of the Finlaggan Archaeological Project, researchers at the University of St Andrews and Smart History have created a new digital reconstruction of Finlaggan as it may have appeared in the fifteenth century – in the latter phase of its medieval glory days.

There is a video preview of the reconstruction on [Vimeo](https://vimeo.com/4748691).

A 360° tour can be found on [Roundme](https://roundme.com/4748691).

You can walk through the reconstruction as part of the VR exhibit at the [Finlaggan Visitor Centre](https://www.finlaggan.org.uk/visitor-centre).

3D Objects

List of 3D objects published on Zenodo.

The Finlaggan Cross – 3D Model DOI:

Slate Carved with a Heraldic Lion - 3D Model [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4749332](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749332)

Quern Stone – 3D Model [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4749356](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749356)

Wooden Hilt – 3D Model [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4749347](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749347)

Bone Comb – 3D Model [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4749323](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749323)

Crucifix Part – 3D Model [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4749315](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749315)

Game Piece – 3D Model [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4749312](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749312)

APP

The app, [Lords of the Isles: 15th Century Finlaggan](#), guides you through the reconstruction

Associated Resources

A tour of the reconstruction and objects, and the research behind them, by David Caldwell as part of the Heritage at Home series can be found [here](#).

A tour of the site today is viewable [here](#), as part of the [Lordship of the Isles series](#).

An interactive map of the associated sites can be found [here](#).

How Has the Gallery Been Used?

It is part of the wider [CINE](#) project which focuses on digitally representing heritage in northern environments.

When Was the Gallery Published?

The gallery was compiled on the CINE Gate website in 2018.

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Discover More

Information held by Historic Environment Scotland about Finlaggan can be accessed via [Canmore](#). CANMORE

You can see how Loch Finlaggan looks today on [Google Maps](#).

The full history of the site, including Finlaggan Castle, can be read at [Wikipedia](#). **W**

More information about the project can be found on the [Open Virtual Worlds website](#).

Media

BBC: [Lords of the Isles medieval home in Islay recreated](#)

Scotsman: [Inside the medieval home of the Lords of the Isles](#)

Project Funding

This reconstruction was part of the Lords of the Isles project. The project received funding from the [Finlaggan Trust](#).

This reconstruction was part of the [CINE](#) project for digital heritage in northern environments. The project received funding from the European Union's [Northern Periphery and Arctic Programme](#).